

Visualization of Individual Feature Amount Appearing in Daily Performance Based on Electrostatic Induction

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Abstract: In this paper, a new technique to measure daily human body motion without using cameras and video images is presented. The change in the electric potential of the human body that is caused by the daily performance induces an electrostatic induction current in the electrode placed at a distance of a few meters from the human body. Using this technology, I have developed an effective non-contact technique for the detection of human daily performance by detecting the change in this human-generated body charge. This technique based on the detection of an electrostatic induction current of the order of approximately sub-picoamperes flowing through an electrode that is placed at a distance of 5 m from the subject. It is shown that the characteristics of the individual are included in walking motion, sitting on a chair and retiring motion. This technique effectively explains the behavior of the waveform of the electrostatic induction current flowing through a given measurement electrode through a capacitance model of the human body.

Keywords: Daily performance, Electrostatic induction current, Non-contact measurement, Wavelet transform

I. INTRODUCTION

If it becomes possible to develop technology that makes it easy to extract personal characteristics from daily activities, it will be possible to apply to various fields such as elderly support. Then, by accumulating temporal changes in feature values of the daily living behavior of the elderly, life support of elderly people will be possible. However, there are some difficulties when measuring the behavior of everyday life by the conventional method. For example, when image measurement using one camera is performed, ingenuity to reduce the blind spot of the camera is required. Also, when monitoring with a camera, it is necessary to pay attention to the subject's privacy. As a method of measuring a human body motion, there is a method based on motion capture using a multi-camera system [1], for example. In this method, it is possible to detect motion such as walking motion by detecting the movement of the marker attached to the human body in the calibrated space with a multi-camera system. However, detection is possible only in a limited space, and the device is also expensive, so it is not easy to use it in general household.

Meanwhile, a method for detecting daily performance by attaching an electromyograph, a strain gauge, and an accelerometer to the body is used. However, since the subjects are always wearing sensors such as accelerometers, the subject's life becomes troublesome. Therefore, in the conventional method, it was difficult to acquire natural daily performance in a completely non-contact condition without attaching instruments to subjects.

The author thought that if it was possible to detect only the change in the human body potential in a non-contact condition, it will be possible to detect the natural walking motion of the subject without wearing the sensor to the subject. It has been known that the potential fluctuation of the human body occurs with human body movement. Conventional electrostatic discharge studies have used contact type electrodes when measuring human body potential. Therefore, in the conventional method, when measuring the potential of the human body that changes according to the movement of the subject, the subject measured the measurement electrode in close contact with the human body. Therefore, since it is always necessary to attach the electrode to the subject, a method of directly

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measuring the human body potential is not practical. In addition, human body potential may rise to about 10 kV in everyday life. A potential fluctuation of about 10 V due to walking motion is superimposed on a high voltage of 10 kV. Therefore, it is extremely difficult to obtain a walking signal by directly measuring the human body potential. The author thought that if it was possible to detect only changes in the human body potential in a non-contact condition, it would be possible to detect the natural motion of the subject without bringing the sensor etc. into close contact with the human body. Therefore, a device has been developed to measure human body potential fluctuation accompanying the movement of the human body by detecting a weak current induced in the electrode near the subject. By using this device, it was shown that peaks occurred at the timing of foot contact and detachment due to walking exercise are observed in the electrostatic induced current waveform detected with stepping motion and walking motion. Furthermore, the author has constructed a theoretical model clarifying the cause of generating an induced current by walking motion. In this research, in order to detect subject movement more easily, the author developed a portable wireless sensor with the electrode inside the sensor. Using this sensor, non-contact measurement was performed on the subject's daily performance. The walking signal detected by this sensor was collected wirelessly by the data collecting PC by the wireless transmitter. In addition, a system was developed to analyze signal waveforms obtained in real time using LabVIEW.

II. PRINCIPLE

The principle of the measurement technique described above will be explained by taking walking motion as an example. Electric charge is generated in the human body during walking [2-4]. In the case of a subject who is standing, we assume that there are two highly resistive layers between the feet of the subject and the floor. One layer is the sole of the subject's footwear. The other layer is the surface of the floor. The capacitance C_{sf} of the feet relative to the ground may be calculated as the sum of the capacitance of the sole, C_s , and the capacitance of the surface of the floor, C_f , as shown below [5]:

$$\frac{1}{C_{sf}} = \frac{1}{C_s} + \frac{1}{C_f}, \quad (1)$$

Therefore, the potential U_B of the human body during the walking motion can be expressed as follows:

$$C_x = \frac{\varepsilon_a S_{nc}}{(x-x_0)} + \frac{\varepsilon_f S_c}{x_0} = \frac{\varepsilon_a S_{nc} x_0 + \varepsilon_f S_c (x-x_0)}{(x-x_0)x_0}, \quad (2)$$

where Q_B is the instantaneous charge on the human body during the walking motion. The induced charge Q of the measurement electrode placed at a certain distance from the subject can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{1}{C_B} = \frac{1}{C_{sf}} + \frac{1}{C_x}, \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the potential U_B of the human body during the walking motion can be expressed as follows:

$$U_B = \frac{Q_B}{C_B} = \frac{Q_B}{C_{sf}} + Q_B \frac{(x-x_0)x_0}{\varepsilon_a S_{nc} x_0 + \varepsilon_f S_c (x-x_0)}, \quad (4)$$

where Q_B is the instantaneous charge on the human body during the walking motion. The induced charge Q of the measurement electrode placed at a certain distance from the subject can be expressed as follows:

$$Q = C(V - U_B), \quad (5)$$

where C is the capacitance between the human body and the measurement electrode, and V is the potential of the measurement electrode. From the abovementioned equations, the induced current I flowing through the measurement electrode can be expressed as follows:

$$I = -Q_B \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{(x-x_0)x_0}{\varepsilon_a S_{nc} x_0 + \varepsilon_f S_c (x-x_0)} \right), \quad (6)$$

When the differentiation of the right-hand side of Eq. (6) is executed, the following equation is obtained.

$$I = \frac{Q_B}{\{\varepsilon_a S_{nc} x_0 + \varepsilon_f S_c (x-x_0)\}^2} \times \left[-x_0^2 \varepsilon_a S_{nc} \frac{dx}{dt} + (x-x_0)x_0^2 \varepsilon_a \frac{dS_{nc}}{dt} + (x-x_0)^2 x_0 \varepsilon_f \frac{dS_c}{dt} \right], \quad (7)$$

We assume that the human body is a good conductor of electricity. The first term on the right-hand side of Eq. (7) represents the current induced by the motion of the subject's foot and leg after the foot is lifted off the floor. The first term is approximately proportional to the velocity of motion of the foot. The second term on the right-hand side of Eq. (7) is a term proportional to the time differentiation of the peeling area S_{nc} between the sole and the floor surface. Further, the third term on the right-hand side of Eq. (7) is a term proportional to the time differentiation of the contact area S_c between the soles of the sole and the floor surface. Here, since the average dielectric constant ϵ_f of the material from the floor surface to the earth is several times larger than the dielectric constant ϵ_a of the air, the third term on the right side of the equation is sufficiently larger than the first term and the second term. Therefore, when the walking motion takes place near the measurement electrode, it is possible to measure the current generated under perfect non-contact conditions. In other words, the equation shows that the signal proportional to the time differential of the foot sole contact area is strongly reflected in the electrostatic induction current induced by the walking motion of the human.

III. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The potential fluctuation of the human body caused by walking and seating motion of the subject induces the electrostatic induction phenomenon in the measurement electrode in the vicinity of the subject. A temporal change in the potential induces a weak and transient electrostatic induction current in the electrode as small as pA. The induced electrostatic induction current was converted to a voltage with the I - V converter shown in Fig. 1. In order to convert a weak current into a voltage, a low-noise operational amplifier with an input offset voltage of $40 \mu\text{V}$ and an input offset current of 1 pA was used for I - V conversion. The feedback resistance R_f was set to $3 \text{ T}\Omega$, and the feedback capacitance C_f was set to about 1 pF . A feedback capacitor was constructed by winding a tin-plated copper wire with a diameter of 0.6 mm around a feedback resistor. The feedback capacitance C_f increases as the position where the tin plating wire is wound around the resistance are moved to the input side of the operational amplifier and decreases as it moves to the output side of the operational amplifier. Furthermore, in order to detect such a weak current, we adopted the layout of guard ring structures that reduces

the leakage current at the input of the operational amplifier. The I - V conversion ratio of the I - V converter is about 3V/pA . This signal contains a lot of noise mainly caused by commercial electric power (60 Hz). Therefore, by using a low pass filter with a cutoff frequency of 20 Hz , noise caused by commercial frequency was cut. Human body motion signals measured in this study do not contain high-frequency components higher than 20 Hz , and it is confirmed that the detection of signals is not affected even by using a low pass filter. In order to more easily measure the motion of the human body, signal detection was made possible by developing a portable wireless sensor as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.1. Schematic circuit diagram of the I - V converter

Fig.2. Photograph of the portable sensor

In this study, we attempted to detect seating and withdrawing motion on a chair as an example of daily activities. In the experiment, seven healthy men (22 to 24 years old) became subjects. The subjects were asked to walk and walk to the chair 5 meters away in the laboratory and sit down and stopped for 5 s then stand up and walk to the original position. This simple

operation was performed five times for each subject, and the electrostatic induction current induced by this operation was measured. In order to avoid the effect of differences in footwear, subjects wore the same footwear (shoe sole made of urethane) and walked on a PVC floor.

In principle, the electrostatic induction current detected in this study is not affected by the temperature, but humidity affects the signal intensity. Especially, in this study, since large feedback resistance is used, the leakage current flowing to the resistance surface increases when the ambient humidity is high. Therefore, in order to prevent the influence of humidity, it is difficult to be affected by humidity by using a hermetically sealed feedback resistor.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 3 shows a typical electrostatic induction current waveform obtained by walking motion. The obtained result shows that the peak is detected in the electrostatic induction current waveform at the timing when the subject's foot contacts the floor and the subject's foot off the floor. This is in agreement with the prediction of the equation (7) that the peak of the electrostatic induced current waveform is detected at the time of contact of the foot or leaving the ground.

Fig.3. A typical waveform of current generated by a human walking motion

Upper figure of Fig. 4 shows the electrostatic induction current induced by the motion of sitting in a chair after walking and stopping for 5 s after walking and then retreating from the chair and walking. This waveform shows that a peak is detected in the electrostatic induction current waveform at the timing of foot contact and detachment due to the walking motion of the subject. Then, during the motion of stopping for 5 s after seating, no signal appears in the

electrostatic induction current. Subsequently, after stopping in the chair for 5 s, a waveform which is retired from the chair and walking motion are detected. The scalogram obtained by the wavelet transformation of the electrostatic induction current waveform detected by this series of motions is shown in the lower figure of Fig. 4. In this study, the basic reference wave used as a mother wavelet is Complex Morlet Wavelets. In this figure, the vertical axis shows logarithmic representation in order to make the change of the low-frequency component easier to understand. By performing the wavelet transformation, the behavior of frequency change in each motion can be visualized.

Fig.4. Electrostatic induction current waveform obtained in daily performance (upper figure) and typical scalogram of electrostatic induced current obtained by wavelet analysis (lower figure)

From the scalogram obtained by the wavelet analysis of Fig. 4, the following matters were clarified. Differences are detected between the motion of sitting on a chair after walking and the motion of walking after retiring from a chair. Signals caused by walking motion are periodically detected in the frequency region above 3 Hz. In the frequency range between 3 Hz and 0.7 Hz, weak parts of the signal are detected in a mottled state, and it can be considered that these signal patterns appearing in the scalogram indicate characteristics of a series of motions. Furthermore, in the low-frequency region of 0.7 Hz or less, signals caused by long-period fluctuations during motion are generated.

Fig.5. Comparison between wavelet analysis patterns of electrostatic induction current generated during human walking and sitting motions

Fig. 5 shows the scalogram by wavelet analysis obtained by 7 subjects. In order to show the reproducibility of the waveform, three motion detection results obtained by each subject are shown side by side. Comparing the three scalograms obtained by each subject, it can be seen that similar patterns are detected in any subjects. This indicates that the characteristics of motion of subjects can be detected with good reproducibility by using the method proposed in this research. In addition, by comparing the scalogram patterns between each subject, interesting results were revealed. First, when we compare the entire scalogram, we found that a unique pattern exists in each series of actions of each subject. In particular, many subjects differ greatly in the pattern of the scalogram of the motions of walking and sitting in a chair and walking while leaving the chair. On the other hand, subject G does not change significantly in the pattern of the scalogram of sitting after walking and walking after

retirement. Also, in the frequency range between 3 Hz and 0.7 Hz, a spotty pattern characteristic of each subject is detected in the scalogram. Furthermore, when patterns in the low-frequency region are compared, there are subjects who do not have signals in the low-frequency region as in subject B, for example. On the other hand, there are subjects who show strong signals in the low-frequency region like the subject D, and features of the subject's low-frequency motion are detected. Therefore, in order to quantitatively evaluate that the motion pattern of the subject was detected in the wavelet analysis diagram, the normalized correlation coefficient was obtained by pattern matching of the scalogram.

Tab.1 Normalized correlation coefficients obtained by wavelet pattern matching for movements of walking and sitting down in a chair

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
A	0.91	0.57	0.77	0.51	0.52	0.54	0.76
B		0.88	0.69	0.31	0.35	0.29	0.54
C			0.83	0.45	0.45	0.55	0.61
D				0.87	0.55	0.63	0.41
E					0.77	0.61	0.51
F						0.75	0.46
G							0.86

Tab.2 Normalized correlation coefficients obtained by wavelet pattern matching for movements of standing up from a chair and walking

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
A	0.83	0.52	0.56	0.54	0.75	0.68	0.38
B		0.79	0.55	0.49	0.63	0.69	0.58
C			0.78	0.51	0.59	0.62	0.65
D				0.85	0.56	0.53	0.61
E					0.88	0.63	0.66
F						0.78	0.64
G							0.91

Regarding the two patterns of "walking and sitting motion" of about 2 s to 7 s in the time domain and "retraction motion and walking motion" of about 11 s to 16 s in the time domain, correlation coefficients were determined by a pattern matching method. The image used for pattern matching between different subjects is the first measurement result shown in Fig. 5. For the same subject, the average of the mutual normalized correlation coefficients of the three measurement results was used. Tab. 1 shows the results of the normalized correlation coefficient of pattern matching obtained by

"walking and seating motion". Each of the subjects shows that their own correlation coefficient is higher than that between the subjects. Tab. 2 shows the results obtained by "withdrawal action and walking". Similarly, it can be seen that the correlation coefficient of itself shows a tendency to be higher than that among subjects. From this result, it was quantitatively clarified that there is a specific motion pattern of each subject in "walking and sitting motion" and "retraction motion and walking".

V. CONCLUSION

The author attempted to detect daily motions in a non-contact condition by detecting electrostatic induction current induced by human body potential fluctuation occurring in daily performance. Seated on a chair after walking exercise and stopped for 5 s, then retreated from the chair and walked was selected as an example of daily performance. As a result, it was clarified that a series of these motions can be detected non-contact by the method of detecting the electrostatic induction current proposed in this research. Furthermore, from the results of the scalogram obtained by the wavelet analysis, a characteristic pattern was detected in the signal in the frequency range between 3 Hz and 0.7 Hz. Furthermore, it was found that characteristic patterns unique to the individual existed in walking exercise, sitting on a chair and retirement from a chair.

By using the method proposed in this research, we believe that it is possible to estimate the changes in the activity amount and the motor function of the subject from the temporal change of the waveform due to

walking motion and daily action. In recent years, as a watching system for senior citizens living alone, services using the usage history of electric pots and refrigerators are provided. However, the use history of home appliances does not reflect the physical condition of the elderly, it is only a trace of life. For example, since the drag of the foot is also reflected in the electrostatic induction current waveform, the method proposed in this research helps to know the physical condition of the exercise function of solitaires elderly.

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